

SKINTIMACY

TOUCH AS DIGITAL INTERACTION AND THE EXPLORATION OF INTIMACY

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ABSTRACT

Skintimacy is an interface that allows for the collaborative manipulation of electronic-based processes through touch. Depending on skin contact, movement and duration of touch, digital and electronic setups can be influenced and controlled. In order to provide diverse opportunities for a playful control of audio, video, motors and other forms of output, a microcontroller is being employed to transfer data to software platforms. This sensor, acting as both a research tool and DIY kit (www.skintimacy.org, 2013), is intended to facilitate the symbolic relationship between physical computing and the sense of touch. The straightforward design of the device allows for experimentation in many different contexts. Taking into account the dynamic nature of skin conductivity, which varies individually, one has the possibility to create highly responsive installations.

In the first part of the workshop we will introduce the participants to haptic and touch-based interfaces, describe our intentions, the qualities and technical characteristics of the Skintimacy kit. In the second part, we will practically conceptualize and design interactive scenarios with the skin-based sensor in order to experience interpersonal touch as digital interaction and its influence on intimacy and personal boundaries. A common discussion on the potentials and limitations of skin-based and "techno-organical" interfaces will close the session.

KEYWORDS: *Interaction Design, Skin-based Interfaces, Experimental Interfaces, Touch, Intimacy*

BACKGROUND

After HCI research advanced the relevance of embodied interfaces (Dourish, 2001) and technological developments are providing electronic devices that are worn continuously closer to the person, traditional physical borders between the human body, and technical devices are about to disappear (Spreen, 2010). This transformative process of shifting borders, induce amongst other social and psychological phenomena, a new spectrum of 'in betweenness'. Novel interaction scenarios will not only emerge between instruments and humans, but also between humans among themselves. To raise awareness, attach value, and add importance to these alternative interfaces, the artistic and scientific activities and works contribute to a constructive debate. For example, the oeuvre of performance artist Stelarc radically emphasizes his claim for a revised understanding of the role of the human body within a digitalized

world (Hauser, 2008). Referring to the skin as a central computer input, research projects like Skinput (Harrison et al., 2010) and Sixth Sense (Mistry et al., 2009) adduced technological evidence of its practicability.

APPROACH

Introduction (Phases 1 and 2)

The workshop serves as an overview of current research and developments of gestural and touch-based interfaces as well as referring discussions about experiential aspects, field of applications and limitations. By introducing the Skintimacy sensor that is being used in the workshop, we present the phenomenon of skin conductivity, its technical setup, and its potential to be applied in conjunction with the Wiring or Arduino

platform. Furthermore, in order to investigate the social relations in everyday life, the utilization of research tools within a frame of open source and DIY approaches (in contrast to studies in a laboratory) will be highlighted.

Making (Phases 3 and 4)

Designing scenarios has become an effective method to project, discuss and picture future use situations of technology (Iacucci et al., 2000). In the making phase the participants will first design use scenarios: short narratives within a specific context in which a gestural or touch-based interaction takes place. Each scenario will be analyzed identifying the actors involved, their relationship between each other, and the relevance of skin and touch in the experience. New possible scenarios will be proposed and will be briefly documented in phone videos or storyboards. At this point, the most important inputs and outputs will be identified, and the prototyping phase will begin, starting with quick lo-fi prototypes and 'hands-on' tinkering with the Skintimacy kit (Figure 1).

To enable all participants, each with different capabilities in the field of soldering and programming, to build working prototypes, we will prepare different hardware setups and provide a set of project samples and tutorials. Thus, each participant will be able to explore the skin-based interface, depending on his/her interests and individual skills.

Figure 1. Skintimacy kit

Figure 2. Testing with prototype

Reflection (Phase 5)

Finally, all participants will present the concepts and prototypes that have been made during the workshop in brief. In this phase, there will be a reflection and discussion about described ideas, individual experiences, and problems that shall raise the participants awareness of possible future scenarios and ethical issues of bodily-close, human-machine interfaces.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

One learning objective is to present an approach for using physical computing as a method to experience and explore social interaction rituals with a focus on interpersonal boundaries and intimacy. We expect participants to get to know this 'designerly' mindset and discover new possibilities for skin-based interfaces, thus creating a shift in perspective on interface design and the potentials of embodied interaction.

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¹ With this term we refer to Nigel Cross' "designerly ways of knowing" by which he means a design knowledge gained through creating, using and reflecting upon the use of artefacts. And especially "knowledge that is inherent in the processes of manufacturing.s"